

THE MAIN TYPES OF USE OF HUMAN CAPITAL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7194038>

Types and components of human capital Despite the fact that society and the state spend the same amounts and forms of human capital investment on all layers and categories of the population, the following types of human capital are formed and prevail: 1. Positive (active) human capital; 2. Negative (inactive) human capital; 3. Negative human capital. 1. Positive (active) human capital is creative (creative) and innovative capital that has fully absorbed the investment spent on it and realized it in the form of development and improvement of society. This is manifested in creativity and improvement, including an increase in the standard of living of the population, an increase in innovative potential, the development of the education system, the development of science, the freedom of information exchange and supply, and the improvement of the population's health. Because the size and quality of human capital is measured by the mentality of the population/person, level of education, life vision and health status. It should be said that investments in science, education, and health care can pay off in a historically short period of time, but it is difficult to change a mentality formed over centuries. Therefore, it is important to combine the world's best experience and knowledge with the positive characteristics of the national / individual mentality.

It is noteworthy that while the experience of developed Western and Eastern countries in socio-economic development is being assimilated in Uzbekistan, serious attention is being paid to these points, that is, the forms of advanced foreign experience that correspond to the national mentality and centuries-old traditions of our people are taken or they are adapted to local conditions. Also, the spiritual and educational activities and preventive measures carried out to protect our national culture, traditions and young people from the harmful effects of some movements and movements in foreign countries have this goal in mind. Human capital, like a concrete person, is a product of a certain civilization, mentality and traditions. 2. Negative (passive) human capital. This type of human capital does not significantly contribute to the country's development and innovative economy, its whole essence is to be a consumer of material opportunities. It can be said that passive human capital consists of people who do not have good education, are employed in simple artisanal (manual) industries, barter-based commerce or non-mechanized agriculture. In Uzbek terms, "black workers", that is, people who work in jobs that do not require qualifications,

constitute passive human capital. 3. The third type of human capital that requires the most analysis and discussion is negative human capital. Negative human capital, as the name implies, means a category that did not bring any benefit to the society from the investments spent on it, and was not suitable for contributing to the development of the economy of the society in which it lives, nor to the improvement of the standard of living, nor to the development of oneself as an individual. In Uzbek terms, the category "that does not benefit either oneself or others" constitutes negative human capital. Violent criminals, drug addicts, corruptors, jobless, alcoholics, free-spirited people - in a word, people who have destroyed the material investment of society and family, and the results of their education, appear as negative human capital. In the example of this category of human capital, it is seen that the investments spent on certain categories of people do not always bring positive results. Negative human capital can often arise as a result of shortcomings in the mentality of the people, the low level of culture of the population, social problems in society, as well as the limitation of freedom and liberties, which are the natural rights of people. In spiritually mature societies, those with negative human capital are given the last chance to get out of their hopeless situation, and their efforts for positive change are supported by society and the state. An example of this is the announcement of amnesty to people who have gone astray on the eve of the Constitution Day or the Independence Day, and cases of assistance given to ex-prisoners to find their place in life. As a result of such social care, citizens who have managed to become negative human capital are released from prisons before the deadline, and then the neighborhood and internal affairs bodies help them find work and provide housing, help them get a new profession or trade. There are many people in our country who got on the right path in this way and returned to the category of positive human capital.

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